

Efficacy of Different Insecticides against Red Flour Beetle, *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) under Laboratory Condition

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Abstract

This study aimed to identify effective and cost-efficient control strategies targeting various developmental stages of the red flour beetle (*Tribolium castaneum*). Bioassay results demonstrated that the second larval instar was the most susceptible among the tested stages, with mean mortality rates of 86.67% for Emamectin benzoate and 100.00% for Imidacloprid. Notably, Imidacloprid, particularly at its tested concentrations on the seventh day after treatment, produced the highest mortality rates, significantly surpassing those achieved with Emamectin benzoate. Furthermore, mortality rates exhibited a clear positive correlation with the duration of exposure.

Keywords: Red flour beetle, *Tribolium castaneum*, insecticide, Emamectin benzoate, Imidacloprid.

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Introduction

In the world, more than 200 species of insects have been identified that attack stored crops and their products (Rajendran and Sriranjini, 2008). Beetles belonging to the order Coleoptera constitute the largest proportion and are mainly responsible for the significant losses in stored grains, which amount to about 57% (Kumar and Kalita, 2017). The most prominent of these insects is the rusty flour beetle (*Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst)), whose adults and larvae attack stored grains and their products, causing significant damage to stored foodstuffs (Bilal et al., 2020). The rusty flour beetle is a minor storehouse pest, but at the same time it feeds on many grains, flours, various seeds, nuts, and a wide range of dried stored products (Bell, 2000). The rusty flour beetle (*T. castaneum*) has one of the fastest population growth rates because of its high reproductive rate and lengthy reproductive lifespan (James et al., 2022). The widespread infestations of storeroom insects on stored grains and their products have prompted serious worries throughout the years. To control and eradicate these insect pests, insecticides made in the form of fumigants such as methyl bromide (Lee et al., 2004) as well as hydrogen phosphide and other compounds (Aljibouri et al., 2011) have been extensively used. Recently, some governments decided to prohibit the use of these products to manage storeroom insects. The Montreal Protocol prohibited the use of bromide gas on January 1, 2005, due to its deleterious effects on the ozone layer. The excessive use of chemical pesticides has resulted in the development of resistance in most insects, as well as the

accumulation of pesticide residues on crops and in the environment. All of these issues have prompted the search for new alternatives and strategies that will result in significant and influential changes in pest management, including the replacement of chemical pesticides with safer bio-based materials to reduce the significant risks these toxic substances pose to humans (Omar et al., 2023). Plant-based insecticides have been utilised as an alternative to chemical pesticides since they are less hazardous to humans and animals while also being repellent and fatal to females (Aimad et al., 2022). This study seeks to identify effective and less expensive techniques for combating various phases of the red rusty flour beetle *T. castaneum*.

Materials and Methods

Stock Cultures of Target Pest

The Department of Plant Protection at the College of Agriculture, University of Kerbala, Iraq, provided the adult *T. castaneum*. In 2000 mL jars with meshed lids, 3000 adult *T. castaneum* insects were incubated with 500 g of wheat flour and yeast in a 12:1 ratio to create insects of comparable ages. After four days, the adults insects were taken out. The cultures were incubated at 70% relative humidity and 27 ± 2 . In order to obtain adults of a similar age, the cultures were sieved as new insects appeared, and all adult insects were taken out and placed in a fresh container with food. The trials were conducted on one-month-old insects

The Effect of Emamectin Benzoate and Imidacloprid on the Mortality Rate of Larval and Adult Stages of the Rusty Flour Beetle, *T. castaneum*

Three concentrations of emamectin benzoate and imidacloprid (0.25, 0.5, and 0.75) g/L and (0.5, 0.75, and 1) ml/L, respectively, were prepared. The prepared pesticide solutions were placed in 100 ml hand sprayers. 9 cm plastic Petri dishes were prepared containing filter paper, and each dish contained 10 second-instar larvae, fifth-instar larvae, and an adult stage. These dishes were sprayed in three treatments with 1 ml of the prepared concentrations of the pesticides, with three replicates for each concentration. The control treatment sprayed the dishes with distilled water only. The dishes were left to dry and after 15 minutes the treated insect stages were transferred with a small brush to other Petri dishes containing 5 g of clean flour. The treated dishes were kept in an incubator at a temperature of $28\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and a relative humidity of $70\pm 5\%$. The percentages of larval death were taken after (1, 3, 5, 7) days of treatment and the corrected percentages of death were calculated according to the Abbott equation (1925). SPSS software was used to analyse the data.

Results and Discussion

Effect of Different Concentrations of the Chemical Pesticide Emamectin Benzoate on the Mortality Rates of Larvae and Adults of *T. castaneum*

The results shown in Table (1) indicate the effect of three different concentrations of Emamectin benzoate on three different insect life stages: the second, fifth, and adult stages, over four time periods (1, 3, 5, and 7 days). The results indicated that second-instar larvae were the most deadly at all dosages tested. After seven days of therapy, mortality rates at 0.75 and 0.5 mg/L were 93.33% and 86.67%, respectively, with extremely significant differences from the other doses studied. The data also indicated the effect of varied pesticide doses on fifth-instar larvae, with the maximum mortality rate at 0.75 mg/L, reaching 100% after seven days of treatment. The results also reveal that mortality rises with increasing concentration, reaching 50.84% at 0.25 mg/L versus 65.83% at 0.75 mg/L.

The adult stage was the least vulnerable to the pesticide, with an 83.33% mortality rate on the seventh day at 0.75 mg/L. The results in the same table reveal quite large differences. Numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of plant-based pesticides in controlling insect pests, due to their active compounds such as alkaloids, toxic compounds, and essential oils. These compounds inhibit the feeding process, leading to the gradual death of the insect. They can also penetrate the insect's body through the respiratory openings, directly affecting the nervous and digestive systems, as indicated by Romeilah et al. (2010). In addition, some botanical pesticides contain compounds that mimic the action of hormones, leading to cellular dysfunction and insect death. Osman et al. (2008) found that plant extracts taken from 27 plant species belonging to 20 plant families showed a significant effect in increasing the mortality rates of the fourth larval instar of both the red flour beetle (*T. castaneum*) and the khapra beetle (*Trogoderma granarium*). The study also showed that the mortality rate increased significantly with increasing treatment concentration.

In the same context, a study by Kim et al. (2003) indicated that plant extracts from 30 species of medicinal and aromatic plants, in addition to five types of volatile oils, showed significant effectiveness in killing the adults of both the rice weevil (*Sitophilus oryzae*) and the cowpea beetle *Callosobruchus chinensis*, with mortality rates reaching 100% within a short period of time, ranging from 1 to 4 days after treatment. Other studies have shown that the effectiveness of these pesticides is due to the presence of secondary metabolites such as alcohols, phenols, saponins, triterpenes, and essential oils, which have a high ability to penetrate the insect's hard outer layer (cuticle) and reach its internal tissues. This penetration leads to direct poisoning and functional collapse of the nervous and digestive systems. Al-Saadi (2001) and Shabaa (2011) confirmed the ability of these compounds to penetrate through flexible areas or through the respiratory openings, effectively contributing to the elimination of adult insects.

Table 1. Effect of Different Concentrations of the Chemical Pesticide Emamectin Benzoate on the Mortality Rates of Larvae and Adults of *T. castanum*

Insects stages	Concentrations mL/L	Time/days				concentration rate
		1	3	5	7	
2 nd larvae instar	0.25	6.67	13.33	36.67	73.33	32.50
	0.5	0.00	40.00	73.33	93.33	51.67
	0.75	6.67	23.33	83.33	86.67	50.00
	Control	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Average time period		3.33	19.16	48.33	63.33	
5 th larvae instar	0.25	10.00	30.00	66.67	96.67	50.84
	0.5	26.67	43.33	80	96.67	61.67
	0.75	30.00	53.33	80.00	100.00	65.83
	Control	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Average time period		16.67	31.67	56.67	73.34	
Adults	0.25	3.33	23.33	26.67	50.00	25.83
	0.5	13.33	33.33	46.67	60.00	38.33
	0.75	16.67	60.00	73.33	83.33	58.33
	Control	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Average time period		8.33	29.17	36.67	48.33	

Note: L.S.D 0.05; Insect stage 3.52; Concentrations 4.07; Time 4.07

Effect of Different Concentrations of the Pesticide Imidacloprid on the Mortality Rates of Larvae and Adults of *T. castaneum*

Treatment with Imidacloprid on various stages of *T. castaneum* resulted in substantial mortality rates, as indicated in Table 2. The highest mortality rate was achieved across all insect stages, with 100% after 7

days of treatment. All treatments and concentrations produced highly significant differences when compared to the control treatment, however no significant differences were found with other concentrations.

Studies on the effect of imidacloprid on the adult and larval stages of *T. castaneum* revealed that mortality increased considerably after 7 days of treatment. Both the pesticide concentration and the time of exposure were found to have a significant impact on toxicity levels. Imidacloprid, a neonicotinoid, is especially efficient at controlling insects because it affects the neurological system (Jaber et al., 2025). The elevated mortality rates in insects treated with imidacloprid are related to the insecticide's enhanced neurotoxicity, which results from its method of action. The efficacy of imidacloprid as an insecticide is highly related to its concentration and time of exposure (Elbert et al., 2023). The insecticide's deadly toxicity stems from its direct targeting of the insect's central nervous system; it operates by blocking nicotinic acetylcholine receptors in the brain, disrupting nicotine-dependent neuronal circuits (Matsuda et al., 2020). Imidacloprid inhibits nerve impulse transmission, causing full paralysis and death of the insect by preventing acetylcholine transmission. Imidacloprid has proven to be a highly efficient pesticide, especially against pest species like *T. castanum* (Krishnanc and Sehna, 2006). Additional research has revealed that this insecticide has a strong effect on all stages of *Anoplophora glabripennis* (Motschulsky), with mortality rising over time (Houchat et al., 2020). In one study, mature Asian longhorned beetles were totally eliminated within two to three weeks of daily imidacloprid exposure. This was linked to the insecticide's fatal and sublethal effects, which greatly led to population loss (Ugine et al., 2011). Another study on the potato beetle, *Leptinotarsa decemlineata*, indicated that imidacloprid coupled with the insecticide thiamothoxam was successful in controlling insecticide-resistant insects. Other research have proven the role of Imidacloprid as a pesticide, as well as its crucial role in pest control programs (Alyokhin et al., 2007).

Table 2. The Effect of Different Concentrations of the Pesticide Imidacloprid on the Mortality of Larvae and Adults of *T. castanum*

Insects stages	Concentrations mL/L	Time/days				concentration rate
		1	3	5	7	
2 nd larvae instar	0.5	70.00	86.67	90.00	96.67	85.84
	0.75	73.33	96.67	100.00	100.00	92.50
	1	73.33	100.00	100.00	100.00	93.33
	Control	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Average time period		54.17	70.84	72.50	74.17	
5 th larvae instar	0.5	50.00	60.00	60.00	100.00	67.50
	0.75	33.33	43.33	83.33	100.00	65.00
	1	40.00	60.00	80.00	100.00	70.00
	Control	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Average time period		30.83	40.83	55.83	75.00	
Adults	0.5	46.67	83.33	96.67	100.00	81.67
	0.75	66.67	80.00	93.33	100.00	85.00
	1	53.33	66.67	100.00	100.00	80.00
	Control	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Average time period		41.67	57.50	72.50	75.00	

Note: L.S.D 0.05; Insect stage 3.50; Concentrations 4.05; Time 4.05

Conclusion

The study of different insecticide including Emamectin benzoate and imidacloprid against stored-product insects (*Tribolium castanum*) found intriguing evidence that, under certain conditions, these

insecticides can effectively reduce postharvest pests. As such, they have the potential to be used in integrated pest management tactics in storage facilities.

References

- Aimad, A., Bourhia, M., Hana, H., Sanae, R., Salamatullah, A. M., Soufan, W., Rihan, H. Z., Ouahmane, L., Youness, E. A., Nouredine, E., & Mohamed, F. (2022). Essential oils from *Artemisia herba alba* Asso., *Matricaria recutita* L., and *Dittrichia viscosa* L. (Asteraceae): A promising source of eco-friendly agents to control *Callosobruchus maculatus* Fab. warehouse pest. *Journal of Chemistry*, 2022, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/2373460>
- Aljibouri, A. A., Abd, A. S., Rasheed, K. A., Mageed, D. M., Hassan, S. M., & Ismail, E. N. (2011). Effect of magnetized salt water on seed germination and seedling growth of Alletiffia wheat cultivar *Triticum aestivum* L. *Journal of Biotechnology Research Center*, 5(3).
- Al-Saadi, T. A. M. (2001). *The effect of some plant extracts on the productivity and mortality of the adults of the southern conpea beetle Callosobruchus maculatus (Fabricius) (Coleoptera: Bruchidae)* (Master's thesis). College of Agriculture, University of Basra. 85 pp.
- Alyokhin, A., Dively, G., Patterson, M., Castaldo, C., Rogers, D., Mahoney, M., & Wollam, J. (2007). Resistance and cross-resistance to imidacloprid and thiamethoxam in the Colorado potato beetle *Leptinotarsa decemlineata*. *Pest Management Science*, 63(1), 32–41. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ps.1305>
- Bell, C. H. (2000). Fumigation in the 21st century. *Crop Protection*, 19(8–10), 563–569. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-2194\(00\)00073-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-2194(00)00073-9)
- Bilal, A., Muhaimamad, R., & Kazam, A. (2020). Damage potential of *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) on wheat grains stored in hermetic and non-hermetic storage bags. *International Journal of Tropical Insect Science*, 40, 27–37. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42690-019-00047-0>
- Elbert, A., Haas, M., & Nauen, R. (2023). Neonicotinoid insecticides: Mechanisms of selective toxicity and resistance development in target pests. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 68(1), 231–250.
- EPA. (2006). *United States nomination of critical use exemptions from the 2008 phase out of methyl bromide: Fact sheet*. U.S. Environmental Protection Agency.
- Houchat, J. N., Cartereau, A., Le Mauff, A., Taillebois, E., & Thany, S. H. (2020). An overview on the effect of neonicotinoid insecticides on mammalian cholinergic functions through the activation of neuronal nicotinic acetylcholine receptors. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(9), 3222. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17093222>
- Jaber, N. K., Khalaf, A. A., & Shafeeq, M. A. A. (2025). Comparison of the toxicity of the pesticide imidacloprid and the bioactivity of *Artemisia herba-alba* alcohol extract against *Tribolium castaneum*. *Journal of Applied & Natural Science*, 17(2), [страницы не указаны]. <https://doi.org/10.31018/jans.v17i2.6456>
- James, F. C., Christos, G. A., David, W. H., & Kun, Y. Z. (2022). *Tribolium castaneum*: A model insect for fundamental and applied research. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 67, 347–365. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ento-080921-075157>
- Kim, S. I., Roh, J. Y., Kim, D. H., Lee, H. S., & Ahn, Y. J. (2003). Insecticidal activities of aromatic plant extracts and essential oils against *Sitophilus oryzae* and *Callosobruchus chinensis*. *Journal of Stored Products Research*, 39(3), 293–303.

- Krishnan, N., & Sehnal, F. (2006). Compartmentalization of oxidative stress and antioxidant defense in the larval gut of *Spodoptera littoralis*. *Archives of Insect Biochemistry and Physiology*, 63(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1002/arch.20135>
- Matsuda, K., Ihara, M., & Sattelle, D. B. (2020). Neonicotinoid insecticides: Molecular targets, resistance, and toxicity. *Frontiers in Physiology*, 11, 51. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2020.00051>
- Omar, M. K., Muhammad, H. A., & Mirkhan, S. M. (2023). Effects of crude plant extracts from five parts of *Melia azedarach* on *Tribolium confusum*. *ARO-Sci Journal, Koya University*, p. 50. <https://doi.org/10.14500/aro.11038>
- Osman, A. M., Ismail, I. Y. H., & Korkis, N. S. (2008). The biological effect of a number of aqueous plant extracts on the rusty flour beetle *Tribolium castaneum* and *Trogoderma ranarium*. *Journal of Researches of the College of Basic Education, University of Mosul – College of Basic Education*, 7(4), 300–316.
- Romeilah, R. M., Fayed, S. A., & Mahmoud, G. I. (2010). Chemical composition, antiviral and antioxidant activities of seven essential oils. *Journal of Applied Sciences Research*, 6(1), 50–62.
- Shabaa, S. H. H. (2011). The effect of fruit extracts of *Datura innoxia* on some aspects of the life performance of the Khapra insect *Trogoderma granarium* (Coleoptera: Dermestidae). *Journal of University of Kufa for Life Sciences – University of Kufa*, 3(2), 186–194.
- Ugine, T. A., Gardescu, S., & Hajek, A. E. (2011). The effect of exposure to imidacloprid on Asian longhorned beetle (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) survival and reproduction. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 104(6), 1942–1949. <https://doi.org/10.1603/EC11076>

